

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FOUNDATIONS OF FORMING STUDENT'S METACOGNITIVE COMPETENCE

Saidvaliyeva Dilafruz Ravshanovna

Named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

Teacher of the Department of Foreign Languages , TUTU

e-mail: saiddilafruz2@gmail.com

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Abstract. This article examines the psycholinguistic foundations of developing student's metacognitive competence. The study analyzes the relationship between language and cognition and highlights the role of neuro- and psycholinguistic mechanisms in the language acquisition process. Particular attention is paid to cognitive and metacognitive strategies, vocabulary development, and the acquisition of qualitative adjectives as essential components of learners' linguistic and cognitive growth.

Keywords: metacognitive competence, psycholinguistics, neurolinguistics, cognitive strategies, metacognitive strategies, independent learning, language acquisition

The psycholinguistic foundations of the formation of metacognitive competence in students are largely related to the interaction between language and the brain. Research in the field of neurolinguistics is aimed at studying language processing processes, psycholinguistic models, and language development in children. In this context, it is important to analyze the processes of students' assimilation of knowledge in the educational process from a metacognitive perspective. The assimilation of adjectives and the semantic meanings assigned to them play an important role in the effective assimilation of information and skills. Therefore, the processes of assimilation of adjectives should be studied in close connection with metacognitive activity.

The psycholinguistic foundations of the formation of metacognitive competence are inextricably linked to the ability of students to self-manage and consciously organize their own learning activities in the learning process. Modern pedagogical and psycholinguistic research shows that the development of metacognitive competence is an important factor in the effective organization of students' independent learning activities. This competence develops through the formation of students' skills in planning, monitoring and evaluating their own cognitive activities.

The development of metacognitive competence in the educational process allows students to be actively involved in the learning process and take a responsible approach to their own learning activities. This approach helps to form internal motivation in students. This motivation develops the ability of students to independently manage their own activities and consciously influence the learning process.

Psycholinguistics studies the cognitive processes that occur in the process of language acquisition, that is, the interaction between thinking, language and speech. For example, M. Dey and M. Sawalmeh in their research emphasize the importance of psycholinguistics in identifying difficulties in the learning process and determining the factors necessary for effective mastery of the language system. The psycholinguistic approach also allows for the analysis of individual and social factors that affect the student's language acquisition process.

Students' active participation in the learning process is also related to their social connections and collaborative activities. In such a collaborative environment, students have the opportunity to express their opinions, solve problems together, and evaluate their own learning strategies. This, in turn, contributes to the formation of metacognitive competence.

Currently, special attention is paid to the study of the strategies that students use in their educational process and the formation of new learning strategies in them. Learning strategies play an important role in the development of metacognitive competence. These strategies are usually divided into cognitive and metacognitive types.

Cognitive strategies are directly related to the language learning process and involve the use of specific and conscious methods in completing learning tasks. Such strategies allow students to understand, remember, and reuse the material being learned. For example, when learning a list of words in a foreign language, a student might read the words repeatedly and then try to memorize them. This method is a repetition strategy, which is a category of cognitive strategies.

However, the learning process is not limited to the use of cognitive strategies alone. In the process of forming metacognitive competence, the learner must first determine what is required of the task, select the appropriate strategy for it, and monitor his or her own performance. These processes are carried out through higher-level mental activity and are called metacognitive strategies.

Metacognitive strategies allow students to consciously plan, monitor, and evaluate their own learning. By using such strategies, students are able to determine the effectiveness of their activities and, if necessary, change their strategies. Therefore, in the process of forming metacognitive competence, it is important not only to provide students with knowledge, but also to teach them to analyze their own learning activities.

In psychological research, the difference between cognitive and metacognitive strategies is often explained by analogy with a control system. Metacognition, that is, the use of metacognitive strategies, is an important factor that allows you to manage and control the learning process. Therefore, metacognitive competence is one of the main tools for effectively organizing students' learning activities.

In the process of developing metacognitive competence, the student first identifies the learning task to be completed. At this stage, the student can ask himself the following questions: what is the task, what type of task is it, and whether a similar task has been completed before. Through these questions, the student deeply understands the task and has the opportunity to choose a strategy that is appropriate for it.

Another effective way to develop metacognitive competence in students is through direct strategy instruction. In this, the teacher shows students how to select and use appropriate strategies to complete a specific task. In addition, through group discussions, students have the opportunity to share their experiences and learn new strategies.

The psycholinguistic foundations of the formation of metacognitive competence in students require, first of all, a deep study of the relationship between language and consciousness. Research in the fields of neurolinguistics and psycholinguistics shows that cognitive and metacognitive mechanisms play an important role in the process of language acquisition. In particular, the acquisition of qualitative vocabulary, vocabulary expansion, and

language-related cognitive activities are among the important factors in the process of language acquisition by students.

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